

OG(H)AM IN OPEN SCIENCE COMMUNITY HUBS AND THE CITIZEN SCIENCES - WIKIDATA

FLORIAN THIERY /w S. C. SCHMIDT, M. TROGNITZ, T. HOMBURG

UK-IRELAND DH ASSOCIATION | ANNUAL EVENT 2024
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK (UCC) | 04. - 05. JUNE 2024

SESSION 3A - TALK 3A.IV

ARCHAEOLOGY AND WIKIDATA

[Wikimedia commons: CC 0](#)

ID	Name	Breite	Länge
001	Korinth	37.91	22.87
002	Pergamon	39.13	27.18
...

Münze

ID	Name	Fundort-ID	Metall
0023	Commodus aus Korinth	001	Bronze
0024	Münze aus Korinth	001	Bronze
...

dokumentiert

Münze-ID	Foto-ID
0023	0049
0023	0050
0024	0051
...	...

Foto

ID	Name
0049	Fundfoto - Avers
0050	Fundfoto - Revers
0051	Fundfoto

[Martina Trognitz for IANUS, CC-BY SA](#)

DATABASES PLAY A CENTRAL ROLE IN ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH

local (offline)

online

online & open

part of LOD

NOT MANY DATABASES ARE ONLINE. FEW OF THEM ARE OPENLY AVAILABLE AND ACCESSIBLE. EVEN LESS ARE PART OF THE LINKED OPEN DATA CLOUD.

I want to compare all greek
amphoras dated between
500 and 400 BCE

[MET \(63.11.6\) CC-0](#)

part of LOD

[MET \(SE67441b\) CC-0](#)

online & open

online

local (offline)

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF RECORDS ACROSS MULTIPLE DATASETS IS DIFFICULT

I could use...

wikidata.org

Do you know Wikidata?

WIKIDATA - A SPARQL(ING) UNICORN?

- ❖ A free and open knowledge base
 - everybody can add and edit
- ❖ Central storage for structured data of **Wikimedia** projects (Wikipedia, Wikivoyage, Wiktionary, Wikisource etc.)

Data in Wikidata is:

- ❖ Available under a free license (CC 0)
- ❖ Multilingual
- ❖ Accessible to humans and machines (GUI & API & SPARQL)
- ❖ Exported using standard formats (JSON, RDF, XML)
- ❖ Interlinked to other open data sets on the linked data web

WHAT IS WIKIDATA?

Items

Label
Description
Alias
Identifier

Statements

Property
Value
Qualifier
Reference

WIKIDATA'S DATA MODEL

Which amphoras with
images are in Wikidata?

USE WIKIDATA SPARQL QUERY SERVICE

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

<w.wiki/8Xh>

WHICH AMPHORAS WITH IMAGES ARE IN WIKIDATA?

commons:Hydria des Schuwalow-Malers ...
Q Hydria des Schuwalow-Malers Heidelber...

commons:Hydria des Schuwalow-...
Q Hydria des Schuwalow-Malers Hei...

commons:Hydria des Schuwalow-Malers aus Capua, 430 v. Chr. (...)
Q Hydria des Schuwalow-Malers Heidelberg B 133

commons:Antikmuseum der Universität Heidelberg 57-8.jpg
Q Kylix des Providence-Malers

commons: Böotischer-geometrischer großer ...
Q Böotischer Krater

commons:Protokorinthische Oinocho...
Q Protokorinthische Oinochoe

commons:Fragment einer attisch-schwarzfigurigen Trinkschale aus Phaleron I...
Q Namensvase des Heidelberger Malers

commons:Fragment einer attisch-schwarzfigurigen Trinkschale aus Phaleron im ...
Q Namensvase des Heidelberger Malers

commons:Terracotta volute-krater (bowl fo...
Q Volutenkrater des Malers der wollenen Sat...

commons:Terracotta aryballos (oil flask...
Q Keramik-Aryballos, signiert von Nearchos

AMPHORAS WITH IMAGES AS IMAGE-MAP

[Hadley Wickham and others at RStudio \[CC BY-SA 4.0\]](#)

SPARQL UNICORN GOES R

Which motives are on
wikidata greek amphoras,
queried using R?

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

<w.wiki/9Er>

WHICH MOTIVES ARE ON WIKIDATA GREEK AMPHORAS, QUERIED USING R?

Capreolus (Q1043583)
genus of mammals *Englisch*

Museum August Kestner [CC BY-SA 3.0]

Query: [w.wiki/9Er](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/9Er)

EXAMPLE QUERY RESULT FROM 2019

Which castles that are archaeological sites are on Wikidata, queried using R?

A screenshot of the Wikidata Query Service interface. The header shows the Wikidata logo, the text "Wikidata Query Service", and buttons for "Examples", "Help", and "More tools". Below the header, there is a text input field containing "1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)". The main content area displays a 3D model of a stone castle with two towers and a red tiled roof. To the right of the castle is a large red question mark and the text [w.wiki/9Ew](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/9Ew). On the left side of the interface, there is a vertical toolbar with various icons for editing and sharing.

WHICH CASTLES (ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES) ARE ON WIKIDATA, QUERIED USING R?

Corfe Castle (Q1236511)

fortification in Dorset, England

[Chin tin tin \[CC BY 3.0\]](#)

Query: [wwiki/9Ew](#)

EXAMPLE QUERY RESULT FROM 2019

OGHAM AND WIKIDATA

OGHAM @ WIKIDATA

OSM @ WIKIDATA

OpenStreetMap element (P10689) : vei eller punkt i **Open Street Map** for denne tingen. hvis mulig benytt istedenfor

"OpenStreetMap relation ID" (P402). *Norwegian Bokmål*

way or node in OpenStreetMap for the item

38 statements, 0 sitelinks - 16:27, 4 March 2023

OpenStreetMap relation ID (P402) : **Open Street Map** sasaistes ID *Latvian*

identifier for a relation in OpenStreetMap

54 statements, 0 sitelinks - 17:30, 16 February 2023

WIKIDATA PROPERTIES FOR LINKING RESOURCES
WITH OSM ELEMENTS AND RELATIONS.

TOWNLANDS @ WIKIDATA

- Main page
- Community portal
- Project chat
- Create a new Item
- Recent changes
- Random Item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page

Item [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [View his](#)

Coumeenoole North (Q104309699)

townland in Dunquin, County Kerry, Ireland

[edit](#)

[in more languages](#)
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Coumeenoole North	townland in Dunquin, County Kerry, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	townland ~ 0 references
-------------	--

[HTTPS://WWW.LOGAINM.IE/GA/22572](https://www.logainm.ie/GA/22572)

Identifiers

Logainm ID	22572	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
OpenStreetMap relation ID	4250372	edit
	~ 0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

OGHAM SITES @ WIKIDATA

Statements

instance of	Ogham Site	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
located in the administrative territorial entity	Munster	edit
	1 reference	
	Corkaguiny	edit
	1 reference	
	Dunquin	edit
	1 reference	
	Dunquin	edit
	1 reference	
	Coumeenoole North	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

coordinate location

52°6'36.8914"N, 10°28'23.4887"W

[1 reference](#)

reference URL <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/5145413640>

described at URL	https://www.townlands.ie/en/kerry/corkaguiny/dun-chaoin/toghroinn-ceantair-dun-chaoin/com-dhineol-thuaidh/	edit
	<small>critierion used townlands.ie - Irish Townlands</small>	
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value
exact match	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000083	edit
	0 references	+ add reference
		+ add value

COUMEENOOLE NORTH / TOWNLAND (Q104309699)

OGHAM STONE CIIC 178 BY MACALISTER @ WIKIDATA

instance of

- ogham stone
 - ▶ 1 reference
- Ogham Stone Concept
 - ▼ 0 references
- Ogham Stone Concept (RAS Macalister)
 - ▼ 0 references

 edit

CIIC 178 (Q70892682)

OGHAM STONE CIIC 178 BY MACALISTER @ WIKIDATA

location of discovery		
+ add value		
inscription		
+ add value		
exact match		
+ add reference		
+ add value		

OpenStreetMap element	node/5145413640
▼ 0 references	

CIIC 178 (Q70892682)

EX-SITU OGHAM STONE WITH ON-SITE SURVEY

OGHAM STONE: ONLY LITERATURE AS SOURCE

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	 ogham stone edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
 Ogham Stone Concept	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
 Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	edit
	0 references
	+ add reference
	+ add value

VIA <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

51°48′59.58″N, 8°45′57.13″W﻿ / ﻿51.81666111°N 8.76557222°W﻿ / 51.81666111; 8.76557222

- determination method [georeferencing](#)
- object has role [book entry \(Ogham\)](#)
- subject has role [archaeological site](#)
- statement in [academic journal article](#)

[1 reference](#)

- reference URL <https://www.corkhist.ie/wp-content/uploads/files/1931/b1931-020.pdf>
- <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25505959>

EXAMPLE: CIIC 81 → FOUND IN GARRANES (LISHEENAGREINE)

81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680733)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

[In more languages](#)
 Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	81 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	No label defined	No description defined	

Statements

instance of	<div> <div>Q106680733</div> <div>ogham stone</div> <div>edit</div> </div>	<div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div> </div>
	<div> <div>Q106680733</div> <div>Ogham Stone Concept</div> <div>edit</div> </div>	<div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div> </div>
	<div> <div>Q106680733</div> <div>Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)</div> <div>edit</div> </div>	<div> <div>▼ 0 references</div> <div>+ add reference</div> <div>+ add value</div> </div>

FLOREAN THIERY, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

51°53'37.7254"N, 8°29'31.6313"W

location	ex situ
sourcing circumstances	on-site survey
determination method	on-site survey
subject has role	exhibition
stated in	OpenStreetMap

▼ 1 reference

OpenStreetMap node ID 11071361392

EXAMPLE: CIIC 81 → CURRENTLY AT UCC CORK #4

Which ogham stones are available in Wikidata?

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

[w.wiki/9B9](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/9B9)

WHICH OGHAM STONES ARE AVAILABLE IN WIKIDATA?

Stones from
Scotland
Wales
England
have to be integrated

Which ogham stones can
be seen at UCC?

Wikidata Query Service

Examples Help More tools

1 (Input a SPARQL query or choose a query example)

 UCC
University College Cork, Ireland
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh
ucc.ie

?

w.wiki/9B8

WHICH OGHAM STONES ARE AVAILABLE IN WIKIDATA?

Table - 0 27 results in 60 ms

item	geo	label
Q uid 069377860	Point:-8.816333 52.015833	CIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895728	Point:-8.823509 51.955833	CIC 105 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895727	Point:-8.806111 51.991111	CIC 107 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895739	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 112 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 0708952440	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 113 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895736	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 114 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 069385434	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 115 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 0708952436	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 118 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 069385241	Point:-8.794722 51.880956	CIC 117 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895722	Point:-8.757222 51.943388	CIC 127 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895734	Point:-8.809167 52.0075	CIC 128 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895701	Point:-7.969589 52.199444	CIC 282 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895730	Point:-8.305556 52.008611	CIC 61 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895723	Point:-8.175556 51.968444	CIC 63 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 069385424	Point:-8.761667 51.816389	CIC 81 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895704	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 83 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895695	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 85 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895716	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 86 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895696	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 87 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895720	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 88 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895690	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 89 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895712	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 90 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895713	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 92 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895692	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 93 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895706	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 94 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895703	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 95 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)
Q uid 070895697	Point:-8.071111 52.026944	CIC 96 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)

UCC Stone Corridor, Stone 4, CIIC 81
Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

OGHAM AND CITIZEN SCIENCE

@UCC

UCC

University College Cork, Ireland
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh

SFM USING THE KIRI ENGINE APP ON 04/06/2024

F. THIERY, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

F. THIERY, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

F. THIERY, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

UCC STONE #1 / CIIC 103

F. THIERY, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Cork: Ogham Stone CIIC 89/ UCC 7

3D Model

b-unicycling

FOLLOWING

Download 3D Model + Add To </> Embed ↗ Share

Triangles: 1.6M Vertices: 812.8k [More model information](#)

Ogham stone with no. 7 in the UCC collection, exhibited in the Stone Corridor at University College Cork.

Wikidata: [Q70885690](https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q70885690)

SMR no.: C0074-164—

Made in KiriEngine from 82 photos.

MESHLAB AND SKETCHFAB VIEW

OGHAM AND CITIZEN SCIENCE

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Archaeology

Teacher finds stone with ancient ogham writing from Ireland in Coventry garden

Exclusive: Sandstone rock featuring language markings created 1,600 years ago to go on display at museum

Dalya Alberge
Wed 8 May 2024 13.02 CEST
Share

The ogham stone, 11cm long and weighing 139g, was found in an overgrown garden. Photograph: The Herbert Art Gallery and Museum

A geography teacher was tidying his overgrown garden at his home in Coventry when he stumbled across a rock with mysterious incisions. Intrigued, he sent photographs to a local archaeologist and was taken aback to learn that the markings were created more than 1,600 years ago and that the artefact was worthy of a museum.

The rectangular sandstone rock that Graham Senior had discovered was inscribed in ogham, an alphabet used in the early medieval period primarily for writing in the Irish language.

Most viewed

- Live Singapore Airlines flight: British man dead and 30 injured after severe turbulence - latest updates
- British passenger dies after severe turbulence on London to Singapore flight
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CITIZEN SCIENTIST GRAHAM SENIOR FOUND AN OGHAM STONE IN COVENTRY

via <https://finds.org.uk/database/artefacts/record/id/1004478>

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ESS-634484 : Roman coin

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INSCRIBED OBJECT

Unique ID: WMID-63448A

Object type certainy: Certain

Workflow status: Awaiting validation

A sub-rectangular, sandstone rock with ogham script inscribed down three of the four sides. The front and back sides are smooth. The rock is a dark grey colour and likely to be a stn type rock (metamorphic muscovite/slate). The incisions appear to have been done in a single action, not repeated.

It measures 110 ^{mm} in length, 36 ^{mm} wide and 19 ^{mm} thick, to weigh 139 g.

Katherine Forde (University of Glasgow) has confirmed that the markings are those of an ogham inscription. The script is that of an early style, most likely 5th to 6th Century but possibly as early as 4th Century. The script is similar to that on an ogham-inscribed knife handle from Wleaving, in Norfolk. The inscription reads: MALDUMCAL/S/LASS. The first part of the inscription relates to a person's name: Mael Dumcail. The second part is less certain.

Chemical composition of the stone surface is: Al 0.17%; Ca 2.65%; Hf 0.21%; P 0.27%; Pd 2.11%; Rh 2.56%; Cd 4.11%; Sn 8.43%; Sr 11.80%; Fe 67.68%

Find of note status

This is a find of note and has been designated: Regional importance

Inscription: MALDUMCAL/S/LASS

Subsequent actions

Current location of find: The Herbert Museum, Coventry

Subsequent action after recording: Donated to a museum

Chronology

Broad period: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Subsperiod from: Early

Period from: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Subperiod to: Early

Period to: EARLY MEDIEVAL

Date from: Circa AD 400

Date to: Circa AD 500

Dimensions and weight

Quantity: 1

Length: 110 ^{mm}

Width: 36 ^{mm}

Thickness: 19 ^{mm}

Weight: 139 g

Discovery dates

Date(s) of discovery: Thursday 28th May 2020 - Thursday 28th May 2020

Personal details

This information is restricted for your access level.

Other reference numbers

Museum accession number: 2023.32AR

Materials and construction

Primary material: Stone

Completeness: Complete

ESS-634484 : Roman coin

Rights Holder: Birmingham Museums Trust

CC License: [CC-BY-NC-SA](#)

[View](#) [Zoom](#) [Download](#)

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[View](#) [Zoom](#)

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INTEGRATED INTO THE PORTABLE ANTIQUITIES SCHEME (PAS)

Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

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III S

III S
III S
III S
III S
III S
III S

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DESCRIBED WITH FREE IMAGES ...

... A FREE 3D-MODEL ...

via <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q125855438>

- Main page
- Community portal
- Projects chat
- Create a new item
- Recent changes
- Random item
- Query Service
- Nearby
- Help
- Donate

- Lexicographical data
- Create a new Lexeme
- Recent changes
- Random Lexeme

Tools

- What links here
- Revised changes
- Special pages
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI
- Cite this page
- Get shortened URL
- Download QR code

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone from Coventry (Q125855438)

No description defined
WMID-83446A ✎ edit

+ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone from Coventry	No description defined	WMID-83446A
German	Oghamstein aus Coventry	2009 antiochischer Oghamstein, jetzt in der Sammlung im Museum in Coventry	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

✎ edit Wikipedia (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikibooks (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikiquote (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikiquote (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikisource (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikiversity (0 entries)

✎ edit Wikivoyage (0 entries)

✎ edit Wiktionary (0 entries)

✎ edit Multilingual sites (0 entries)

Statements

instance of ✎ edit

- ✎ edit ogham stone ✎ edit
- ✎ edit Ogham Stone Concept ✎ edit

+ 0 references ✎ edit

+ add reference ✎ edit

+ add value ✎ edit

image ✎ edit

WMID-83446A.jpg
10,480 × 5,720; 16.82 MB

+ 0 references ✎ edit

+ add reference ✎ edit

+ add value ✎ edit

collection ✎ edit

- ✎ edit Herbert Art Gallery and Museum ✎ edit

+ 0 references ✎ edit

+ add reference ✎ edit

+ add value ✎ edit

location of discovery ✎ edit

- ✎ edit Coventry ✎ edit

+ 1 reference ✎ edit

... AND WIKIDATA!

via <https://www.theguardian.com/science/article/2024/may/08/teacher-finds-stone-ancient-ogham-writing-ireland-coventry-garden>

Teresa Gilmore, an archaeologist and finds liaison officer for Staffordshire and West Midlands based at Birmingham Museums, said : “This is an amazing find. The beauty of the Portable Antiquities Scheme is that people are finding stuff that keeps rewriting our history.

“This particular find has given us a new insight into early medieval activity in Coventry, which we still need to make sense of. Each find like this helps in filling in our jigsaw puzzle and gives us a bit more information.”

When Senior sent her some photographs, she immediately saw its potential. She contacted Katherine Forsyth, professor of Celtic Studies at the University of Glasgow, who confirmed that it was an ogham script, that of an early style, which most likely dates to the fifth to sixth century but possibly as early as the fourth century.

Gilmore said such stones were “very rare and have generally been found in Ireland or Scotland ... so to find them in the Midlands is actually unusual.”

She suggested it could be linked to people coming over from Ireland or to early medieval monasteries in the area. “You would have had monks and clerics moving between the different monasteries.”

The stone, which is 11cm long and weighs 139g, is inscribed on three of its four sides.

Its purpose is unclear, said Gilmore, adding: “It could have been a portable commemorative item. We don’t know. It’s an amazing little thing.”

Explaining its inscription, “Maldumcail/ S/ Lass”, Gilmore said: “The first part relates to a person’s name, Mael Dumcail. The second part is less certain. We’re not sure where the S/ Lass comes from. It is probably a location. So something like ‘had me made’.”

Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY 4.0

THE NEWSPAPER ARTICLE GIVES SOME INFORMATION, HOWEVER ...

“The angle with the most ogham stokes has what looks like **MOULDUMEAIL**. However, it makes more sense to read it as **MAELDUMCAIL** or perhaps **MAELDUMEAIL** - the problem is that the exact position of the stemline is uncertain and the vowel strokes are long like the consonant strokes. The initial M looks quite different to the other strokes (also slants the opposite direction to the other M) and may just be damage to the stone (hence the underdot in transcription).

On two other angles:
 S
 LASS

This could of course also be read the opposite direction.”

Birmingham Museums Trust, CC BY 4.0

... TRUST IN THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXPERTS.

The adjective **máel** (<https://dil.ie/31242>) 'crop-headed, shorn, tonsured' is a commonly found first element in early Irish (religious) personal names (examples here <https://dil.ie/31244>).

However, the second element **-dumeail** or **-dumcail** isn't clear. **Dumeail** is reminiscent of **DUMELEDONAS** (CIIC 368), **DUMELI** (CIIC 252), **DDUMILEAS** (CIIC 198) in ogham inscriptions, but the meaning is unknown and the element doesn't seem to be attested in later manuscript sources.

It's hard to say much about S and LASS but the sequence lass- is found in some later inscriptions, e.g. lassa·ndernad “for whom it has been made” (<https://emili.celt.dias.ie/LOU-001>).

There are also names that begin **lass-**, e.g. **Lassar** 'flame, fire' (<https://dil.ie/29600> or <https://www.dib.ie/biography/lassar-a4690>).

NICE TO KNOW

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Dumeledonas (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Rhys/1907, 80--81: 'The name Dumeledo, genitive Dumeledonas, claims kinship with Dumelus of the stone at Llanddewi-brefi...The meaning of the name Dumel-, eludes me; and I have to make the same confession as to the ending -edu or -edo.'

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/ldwke_1.html

Rhys, J. (1874):	--]MAQI[--] [--] TAQOLEDEMU[--] Expansion: [--]MAQI[--] TAQOLEDEMU Rhys/1874 19 reading only Westwood/1876 93 reading only
Rhys, J. (1906):	MAQI M[--] DUMELEDONAS Expansion: MAQI MUCOI DUMELEDONAS Translation: <i>Son of the kin of Dumeledonas (PN).</i> Macalister/1945 351 reading only Rhys/1877 398 reading only Rhys/1907 78--80 reading only Thomas/1994 98 reading only
Macalister, R.A.S. (1922):	--]MAQI M[--] TUMELEDONAS Expansion: --] MAQI MUCOI TUMELEDONAS Macalister/1922 22 reading only
Nash-Williams, V.E. (1950):	DUMELEDONAS MAQI M[--] Expansion: DUMELEDONAS MAQI MUCOI [--] Translation: <i>(The stone) of Dumeledo, son of the kin of...</i> Nash-Williams/1950 113 reading only

DUMELEDONAS (CIIC 368; CISP LDWKE/1)

Ogham in 3D, CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland,
via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/252_Gurran

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/guran_1.html

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): DUMELIMAQIGL ||| ASIC ||| ONAS | NIOTTACOBTRAN || OR[-
Expansion:
 DUMELI MAQI GLASICONAS NIOTTA COBRANOR[IGAS]
[Macalister/1945](#) 247 reading only

McManus, D. (1991): DUMELIMAQIGL ||| ASIC ||| ONAS | NIOTTACOBTRAN || [O]R[-
Expansion:
 DUMELI MAQI GLASICONAS NIOTTA COBRANOR[-
[McManus/1991](#) 65 reading only

[Dumeli](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

[Glasiconas](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

See McManus 1991, 110, for discussion of the idea that GLASICONAS equated to *c* ◆ *glas*, an immigrant from outside Ireland.

McManus/1991, 102--105, 'GLASICONAS (*Glaisiuc*, gen. *Glaschor*) ... ('grey' + 'wolf').

[Cobranor\[igias\]](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

Wikidata

252 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680996)

Ogham Stone, Ireland

in most languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	252 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

instance of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ogham stone Ogham Stone Concept Ogham Stone Concept (Research Squirrel Ogham Project)
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<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q106680996>

DUMELI (CIIC 252; CISP GURAN/1)

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via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/198_Coolmagort_I

https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/coolm_2.html

Macalister, R.A.S. (1945): MAQIRITEASMAQIMAQIDDUMILEAS | MUCOITOICACI
Expansion:
 MAQI-RITEAS MAQI MAQI-DDUMILEAS MUCOI TOICACI
[Gippert Web 198](#) reading only [[Gippert 198](#)]
[Macalister 1945](#) 193 reading only
[McManus 1991](#) 65 reading only

Maqi-Riteas (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 109: 'MAQI-RITEAS ... (*Mac Rithe*)'.
Maqi-Ddumileas (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 109: 'MAQI-DDUMILEAS (gen. *Duimle*)'.
Toicaci (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
 McManus 1991, 53: 'Three of the seven stones at Coolmagort, County Kerry [i.e. this stone and COOLM/1 and COOLM/4] ... Appear to commemorate members of the *toath* of **Toicacas*'.

WIKIDATA

198 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project) (Q106680892)

Ogham Stone, Ireland edit

in more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	198 (Ogham Stone Concept by the Research Squirrel Ogham Project)	Ogham Stone, Ireland	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
Italian	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

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<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q106680892>

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DUMELI (CIIC 198; CISP COOLM/2)

FINIS!

QUESTIONS?

